

STUDIES IN THE COAGULATION OF COLLOIDS.
PART XVII. THE ANOMALOUS COAGULATIVE
POWER OF AQUEOUS MERCURY CHLORIDE

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The present problem arose out of certain unexpected results to be published shortly, on changes of viscosity and transparency observed in a number of colloids in the presence of some *non-electrolytes*. A consideration of its remarkably low electrolytic conductivity, both in the fused (Biltz, *Z. Physik*, 1926, 36, 36) and the dissolved state (Carnegie and Burt, *Chem. News*, 1897, 75, 174; Biltz, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 40, 199) and its Raman effect (Krishnamurti, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1930, 5, 651) and other properties make one regard mercury chloride as almost a non-electrolyte, behaving principally *covalently*. Its familiar use as an analytical reagent, as also its rôle in not a few inorganic reactions, however, suggests that the other and the opposite electrovalent aspect of its behaviour might not be negligible. It was considered to be of some interest, therefore, to investigate if an examination of its coagulative power would throw some light on the above question. While a definitive decision does not seem permissible at the present stage, the results obtained supply information in a hitherto unexplored line and the complexity of the rôle of mercury chloride has been brought out; the latter was noticed in earlier work on the anomalous changes of the viscosity and transparency in colloids in its presence (Joshi and Kulkarni, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1936, 13, 439; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 103).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The coagulative powers have been examined in the case of eleven colloids in respect of mercury chloride, barium chloride and aluminium chloride. Most of the sols were prepared and their colloid contents determined as described in an earlier paper (Joshi and Jagannath Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 217). The gold sol was prepared by adding 10 c.c. of 0.38% of gold chloride solution to 200 c.c. of redistilled water in a Jena flask and made alkaline with 10 c.c. of 0.2 N- K_2CO_3 . The solution was next heated and when it came to boiling, 5 to 6 c.c. of 0.3% formalin were added drop by drop with continuous stirring. A clear transparent red sol was obtained: this was not dialysed (*vide infra*). A similar method was used to prepare colloidal

silver starting with silver nitrate ($N/200$), ammonia and formaldehyde. Fixed volumes (5 c.c.) of the colloid and each of the differently concentrated coagulator solutions were mixed. The reciprocal of C , the coagulator concentration expressed as millimols per litre required just to cause incipient flocculation, denotes the coagulator power. It is known that this quantity depends upon the manner of addition, stirring, etc., the temperature, concentration of the colloid and, therefore, it lacks an absolute value. For purposes of a comparative survey under a given set of conditions and using a fixed procedure, the coagulative powers, thus determined, were found to be sufficiently accurate and reproducible. These results for C , the precipitating concentration and C. P., the coagulative power are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Sol.	KCl		BaCl ₂		HgCl ₂		AlCl ₃	
	C.	C.P.	C.	C.P.	C.	C.P.	C.	C.P.
MnO ₂	14.7	67.9	0.2470	4042	0.4296	2328	0.8170	1224.0
As ₂ S ₃	56.3	17.8	0.6400	1563	0.2484	4026	0.08525	1730.0
Fe ₂ O ₃	12.3	81.7	0.7690	1300	0.3141	3184	0.1149	8706.0
An (un-dialysed)	16.8	59.5	0.2080	4800	0.4014	2492	—	—
Sb ₂ S ₃	39.2	25.5	0.3720	2689	0.2970	3367	0.2333	4286.0
V ₂ O ₅	20.4	49.1	0.2710	3687	0.3956	2528	0.0924	10820.0
Ag (un-dialysed)	8.8	113.7	0.1780	5615	0.1561	6409		
CuS	23.2	43.1	0.7390	1353	0.5347	1870	0.3796	2634
Cu-ferro-cyanide	11.1	90.4	0.2520	3968	0.5907	1692	0.1021	9790
Prussian blue	125	7.98	3.48	287	5.051	198	0.5129	1950
CdS	46.6	215	0.4450	2247	0.2692	3715	0.07635	

C = precipitating concentration in m. moles ; C. P. = coagulative power.

DISCUSSION.

It is seen from the foregoing results that, as is to be anticipated from general experience (and but partially indicated by the so-called Wetham's law for the relation between c.p., the coagulative power and the valency of the significant ion), there is on the whole a very rapid increase in c.p. according to the series, $KCl < BaCl_2 < AlCl_3$. The coagulative power c.p. for mercury chloride is seen to be almost as high as the bivalent barium ion and in not a

few cases, distinctly greater. The present stage of development of the theory of the mechanism of the coagulative action does not allow of even a semiquantitative specification of C.P. in terms of known and simpler factors. The well known Hardy-Schulze rule merely gives that the relative precipitating power of an ion increases with (a) valency and its (b) preferential adsorption. The last quantity is almost entirely a specific property of a given colloid towards an added material. This is well illustrated by the wide variation in C.P. of any one of the four coagulants in respect of the colloids examined. Since neutralisation of the micellar charge represents not only the end but substantially the mechanism of coagulation, and since the colloids now studied were all negatively charged, the kation is the chief coagulant. In this connection it might be recorded that as indicated by the absence of change of viscosity and turbidity, positive ferric oxide sols failed to show any coagulation with aqueous HgCl_2 even at high concentrations. The additional determinants of the C.P., besides (a) and (b) mentioned above are : (c) the number of ions per unit volume. This is indicated by the corresponding electrical conductivity, which depends upon the degree of ionisation, ionic charge and the corresponding mobility (reduced viscosity of the medium would appear to favour coagulation usually, though not invariably, cf. Joshi and Iyengar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 570) ; (d) the state of the micellar, ionic and molecular surface hydration ; (e) reduction of the dielectric constant ; (f) H-ion concentration of the system ; (g) capillary activity, which is a sensible influence only in hydrophylic colloids ; (h) the concentration of the coagulating solution, the colloid strength, its age, temperature, mode of preparation and the mechanical treatment, etc. On general considerations it is seen that (g) represents but minor factors, which affect only specially sensitive systems. From data in Table I, the C.P. for HgCl_2 appears to be about as high as the bivalent barium and in fact in 6 out of the 11 colloids examined, distinctly greater. This eliminates (a) as a principal determinant of the relative C.P. for HgCl_2 . This also applies to (h). For want of relevant data of a detailed character, no deduction can be made in regard to (e). Considerable amount of evidence exists however to show that changes in the dielectric constant, whose importance was first brought out by the pioneer work of Kruyt and van Duin (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1914, 8, 269), especially of Wo. Ostwald (cf. Freundlich and Rona, *Biochem. Z.*, 1917, 81, 87), and in detail by Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", p. 463), do not possess generality of application (Mukherjee, Chaudhary and Rai Choudhuri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 493 *et seq.* also Joshi and Lal, *ibid.*, 1933, 10, 247). In regard to (d) although mercury salts would appear to be singular in not forming hydrates, data are not available in the literature for inferring the possible effect of this tendency in inducing

coagulation. With respect to (f) Herstad (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1916, 8, 399) has observed in a detailed study of the gold sol that the presence of H-ions inhibits appreciably the coagulative action of HgCl_2 to an extent dependent on its concentration. It is well known that HgCl_2 hydrolyses sensibly in aqueous solutions (Ley, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 30, 226). Herstad (*loc. cit.*) ascribes the c. p. of HgCl_2 chiefly to HgO produced by its hydrolysis. In fact, according to him the alkalinity of the medium is essential for HgCl_2 to act as a coagulant. It is interesting to add that during these experiments we found that the gold and silver sols prepared by the well known Zsigmondy method producing a small alkalinity could not be coagulated by HgCl_2 , if dialysed. This result is in accord with the supposition that the OH' ions which are removed during dialysis are essential for coagulation by HgCl_2 . We consider, however, that alkalinity as the source of the high c. p. of HgCl_2 is not entirely satisfactory explanation of all the facts. For example, our results show that the c. p. of HgCl_2 is quite high, higher than BaCl_2 in such colloids as As_2S_3 , Sb_2S_3 , CuS , CdS , which are not alkaline and, if at all, faintly acidic. Another fact which goes counter to the above supposition obtains in the case of colloid MnO_2 , which contains traces of KOH produced in its preparation. It is seen that the corresponding c. p. for HgCl_2 is distinctly less than BaCl_2 , the contrary is to be expected if alkalinity produces the high c.p. of HgCl_2 .

The factor 'b) is undoubtedly important. Hago Morawitz, (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1910, 1, 501) noted some parallelism between adsorptions on animal charcoal and colloid gold and that HgCl_2 is adsorbed notably heavily by the former. These findings, however suggestive, fail to cover many cases showing that c.p. and ionic adsorbability do not always vary concomitantly (Dhar and Ghosh, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 628). In this connection it is interesting to point out that Chakravarty and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 297) found that adsorption per g. of MnO_2 varied in the order, $\text{KCl} > \text{BaCl}_2 > \text{AlCl}_3$, which is just the reverse of the order for c.p. (compare Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1919, 23, 208). Work is in progress in these laboratories in order to obtain detailed results for the adsorptions of these coagulants by the above colloids, which will be published shortly.

The above consideration of the various factors for the insufficiency, as a general explanation of the relatively high c.p. of HgCl_2 , had tacitly assumed that HgCl_2 was classifiable with KCl , BaCl_2 and AlCl_3 ; this is far from being the case, since it is practically non-ionised. This is illustrated by the following values for the specific conductivity for 0.25N solutions of HgCl_2 , KCl , BaCl_2 : 0.0001649, 0.030698, 0.024358 mho respectively (as determined by Mr. D. N. oianki in these laboratories). Luther (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 36, 401)

finds the following species in a saturated solution of HgCl_2 at 25° , the concentration being expressed in mols per litre : $\text{HgCl}_2 = 0.26$; $\text{HgCl} = 0.00015$; $\text{H} = 0.00033$; $\text{Cl}' = 0.00048$; $\text{Hg}'' = 10^{-8}$; $\text{HgCl}''_4 = 5 \times 10^{-6}$. It is evident therefore, that the amounts of the significant ionic and molecular material in the mixture are far too low to be an adequate source for the c.p. of HgCl_2 , especially when it is noted that the corresponding solutions of KCl and BaCl_2 due to their almost complete dissociation contain the relevant ions in comparatively very large amounts. The c.p. for a tri- or tetravalent kation is likely to be relatively very high, presumably much higher than AlCl_3 in the case of the latter. The presence of such ions is rendered likely by the claim of Bourion and Rouyer (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, 10, 263) that aqueous HgCl_2 contains products of the following equilibria :

The value of this factor is discounted very appreciably since it is almost certain that the corresponding concentrations of these ionic polymers is extremely small. From a review of these facts taken together it can be concluded that the generality of the relatively high c.p. of HgCl_2 , brought out by our results, can not be ascribed to one or a simple combination of any of the factors postulated in the current theories of the coagulation phenomena, as discussed above, and be best treated as an open question requiring further examination from an experimental stand-point.

S U M M A R Y.

1. Results are given for c.p. the relative coagulative powers of KCl , BaCl_2 , HgCl_2 and AlCl_3 towards negatively charged colloidal solutions of As_2S_3 , Fe_2O_3 , Sb_2S_3 , V_2O_5 , CuS , copper ferrocyanide, Prussian blue, CdS and MnO_2 , Au , Ag (the last three being undialysed and containing a small quantity of OH').

2. The c.p. for HgCl_2 has been found to be about as high as BaCl_2 and in 6 out of 11 cases, greater.

3. Contrary to the conclusions of Herstad, alkalinity is not considered as fundamental to the large value of c.p.

4. The possible influence of the valency, adsorption, H° ions, capillary activity, dielectric constant and especially of the available small kationic concentration are discussed and found to be insufficient for a general theoretical explanation.

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Received January 30, 1937.